

Scenario 5

N1 N2 N3 N4
 0 sample 1
 0 sample 2
 0 sample 3
 0 sample 4
 t1 split 3 4 1 ra
 t2 split 2 4 1 ra
 t3-db VarNe 4 N4b
 t3 merge 1 4

Scenario 6

N1 N2 N3 N4
 0 sample 1
 0 sample 2
 0 sample 3
 0 sample 4
 t1 split 2 4 1 ra
 t2 split 3 4 1 ra
 t3-db VarNe 4 N4b
 t3 merge 1 4

